

“VALEURS CULTURELLES ET ARTISTIQUES D’INTÉRÊT UNIVERSEL”. AESTHETIC AND SCIENTIFIC QUANDARIES AROUND THE UNESCO ANTHOLOGY OF AFRICAN MUSIC

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ABSTRACT

The vision and editorial choices underlying the UNESCO LP series *An Anthology of African Music* resulted from intense negotiations between Paul Collaer, the series’s general editor, and Alain Daniélou, the director of the International Institute for Comparative Music Studies and Documentation (IICMSD), which edited the collection for UNESCO. During the preparation of the records, tensions arose over editorial decisions, as Daniélou’s and UNESCO’s aesthetic approach, favoring artistic refinement and high audio quality, conflicted with Collaer’s documentary focus and recognition of the cultural significance of certain repertoires. This article examines the origin, development, and conclusion of the first part of this record series (1964-1969) and analyzes the negotiations and conflicts surrounding the preparation of specific albums. The tensions regarding the collection’s editorial choices shed light on discussions within ethnomusicology and across institutions focused on traditional musics, as well as on broader perspectives related to international music policies, visions, and priorities in promoting African musics.

“Valeurs culturelles et artistiques d’intérêt universel”. Dilemmi estetici e scientifici intorno alla Anthology of African Music UNESCO. La visione e le scelte editoriali alla base della serie di LP UNESCO *An Anthology of African Music* furono il risultato di intense negoziazioni tra Paul Collaer, curatore generale della serie, e Alain Daniélou, direttore dell’International Institute for Comparative Music Studies and Documentation (IICMSD), che curò la raccolta per conto dell’UNESCO. Durante la preparazione dei dischi emersero tensioni riguardo alle decisioni editoriali, poiché l’approccio estetico di Daniélou e dell’UNESCO – volto a privilegiare il raffinemento artistico e un’alta qualità sonora – entrava in conflitto con la prospettiva documentaria di Collaer, attenta al riconoscimento del valore culturale di determinati repertori. Questo articolo esamina l’origine, lo sviluppo e la conclusione della prima parte di questa serie discografica (1964-1969) e analizza le negoziazioni e i conflitti che accompagnarono la preparazione di alcuni album specifici. Le tensioni riguardanti le scelte editoriali della collezione illuminano i dibattiti interni all’etnomusicologia e alle istituzioni dedicate alle musiche tradizionali, oltre a offrire spunti più ampi sulle politiche musicali internazionali, sulle visioni e sulle priorità nella promozione delle musiche africane.

For many ethnomusicologists and record collectors, the UNESCO LP series *Anthology of African Music* serves as a reference on musical traditions from the African continent. Released by Bärenreiter-Musicaphon between 1965 and 1969 and again in the 1980s after being discontinued, the series was directed by Paul Collaer and edited by the International Institute for Comparative Music Studies and Documentation (IICMSD) under the auspices of UNESCO. Originating from UNESCO policies and orientations around the turn of the 1950s and 1960s and developed in collaboration with the International Music Council (IMC), the African anthology aimed to support UNESCO's goal of fostering peaceful relations among countries by enhancing musical knowledge and thereby encouraging mutual appreciation and respect. It was part of the broader initiative that became the UNESCO *Collection of Traditional Music from the World*, which was initiated by *A Musical Anthology of the Orient*, edited by Alain Daniélou since 1961 (Clouter 2001). The two UNESCO anthologies had «a cultural aim as collections of propaganda for making aware a large audience of the existence of cultural and artistic values of universal interest in the countries of Asia and Africa» (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 13 Nov. 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

Alain Daniélou collaborated with UNESCO beginning in the 1950s as an expert in Asian musics. An eclectic and controversial figure in both music and Southeast Asian studies, Daniélou had a classical music and dance training in his native France before exploring and studying South and Eastern Asian musics and cultures, in particular Indian classical ones, while living for almost two decades in India (Daniélou 1987). This experience was pivotal in shaping his complex aesthetic views of the musics of the world, which combined a firm belief in the equal value of "western" and "Other" musical traditions based on their artistic refinement as well as on the appreciation of their specific musical systems and values (Cimardi 2021). It also determined his commitment to their national and international recognition through the active promotion of Asian artists and ensembles in tours and records in a time when a mainstream craze for "Oriental music" and spirituality – which he despised – also started (Cimardi 2018). Daniélou's partnership with UNESCO strengthened in 1963 with the foundation of the IICMSD in West Berlin, an institute under his direction dedicated to the musics of the world, which established formal consultative relationships with UNESCO.

Daniélou and Belgian musicologist Collaer had known each other since the 1950s and developed a friendship over the years. After a career focused on promoting contemporary music as a concert organizer and serving as the director of the Flemish music service for Belgian Radio, Collaer devoted the latter part of his life to researching traditional musics. He conducted fieldwork in various European regions, authored several publications, and annually organized the international Colloques de Wégimont dedicated to ethnomusicology, where he also invited Daniélou in 1960. Through these symposia and the foundation of what later became the Centre d'Ethnomusicologie in Tervuren, Collaer became a pioneer of Belgian ethnomusicology. It was likely Daniélou who recommended Collaer to the IMC and UNESCO as the general editor for *An Anthology of African Music*. Although not an Africanist, Collaer was involved in another extensive editorial project of global reach, *Die Musikgeschichte in Bildern*, and accepted the direction of the record

series. However, Collaer's approach and vision as general editor led to disagreements with both Daniélou and UNESCO, ultimately contributing to the discontinuation of the series.

While various albums of the "African anthology", as it was usually referred to by Collaer and Daniélou, have been analyzed in several reviews, the editorial work behind the series has never been studied. This article examines the collaboration between the IICMSD, primarily through its director Alain Daniélou, and Paul Collaer, the general editor of the series, in producing *An Anthology of African Music* during the 1960s. It focuses on the conceptions and visions underlying this record series and, more broadly, on the approaches to representing traditional musics through records. During the preparation of the African anthology, the selection, montage, editing, and visual and textual presentation of the music of various African peoples were central to different understandings and debates about traditional music worldwide, especially from Africa, which echoed or challenged discussions both within and outside academia. The scrutiny of the preparations of some albums illustrates clashes between Collaer's positions and those of Daniélou and UNESCO. Examining the challenges in the choices concerning the records allows for an exploration of UNESCO's policies as interpreted and applied by the IICMSD, highlighting discrepancies with contemporary ethnomusicology, to whose principles Collaer adhered. Finally, the discussion reflects on pivotal years for establishing ethnomusicology as an academic discipline, the work of related non-academic institutes like the IICMSD, and the impact of UNESCO's supranational vision of music based on "cultural and artistic values of universal interest" on the representation and dissemination of musics from the African continent.

THE ORIGINS OF THE ANTHOLOGY OF AFRICAN MUSIC: COMBINING DIFFERENT VISIONS

During a meeting gathering experts of traditional music at the Hebrew University in Jerusalem in 1963,¹ Jack Bornoff, IMC Executive Secretary, presented the UNESCO project of *An Anthology of African Music* and requested the advice of the experts summoned there: Hugh Tracey, Klaus Wachsmann, Laura Boulton, Paul Collaer, Kwabena N'Ketia, Tolia Nikoproweztky, Maud Karpeles, and Alain Daniélou. After a discussion featuring the specialists' experiences, it was proposed that the series be issued by the IMC/UNESCO with the collaboration of the IICMSD and edited by a distinguished ethnomusicologist. The series had to cover "negro areas" both North and South of the Sahara, arrangements had to be made with other institutions to avoid overlapping in the records' contents, and areas not documented by existing recordings would be researched through special missions. Daniélou and Bornoff asked Collaer to undertake the editorship ("UNESCO Anthology of

¹ The meeting took place on 7 August, when the 16th IFCM conference also took place in Jerusalem, which is why several ethnomusicologists were present, along with Bornoff, representing the IMC as a co-organizer of the event, and Daniélou, who presented a paper. The conference theme, "East and West in Music", was dear to UNESCO in those years of the *Major Project*. The conference program is available at: [https://www.ictmusic.org/sites/default/files/documents/world%20conferences/programmes/programme%201963%20conference%20\(jerusalem\)-english-french-hebrew.pdf](https://www.ictmusic.org/sites/default/files/documents/world%20conferences/programmes/programme%201963%20conference%20(jerusalem)-english-french-hebrew.pdf) (last accessed: 5 September 2025).

African Music. Report on a meeting of experts" [draft]. AC, box 4, folder 1). This new record series would join the running *A Musical Anthology of the Orient*, edited by Daniélou, with the purpose of «making the musical treasures of Asia and Africa known in Europe and America, and teaching Asians and Africans to preserve the foundations of their own cultures» (IICMSD, "Section d'études africains – Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale, Tervuren". AC, box 5, folder 5).

The idea for such anthologies stemmed from a large initiative that UNESCO implemented for several years, the *Major Project: Mutual Appreciation of Eastern and Western Cultural Values*. This resulted from pressure placed by Asian member countries of UNESCO for the Organization to undertake measures to enhance cultural dialogue between what were commonly framed as the Orient and Occident (Huttunen 2016; Wong 2008). This decade-long project (1957-1966) encompassed various cultural fields – literature, history, visual arts, architecture, cinema, and music – and aimed to dismantle stereotypes and foster reciprocal knowledge between these cultural regions. The ambiguity surrounding the concepts of East/Orient and West/Occident, as addressed by the project, was evident from the outset and UNESCO opted for flexibility in delineating the geographical areas (Huttunen 2016). This strategy accommodated the Organization's progressive expansion into new countries that were gaining independence during those years and aligned with its inclusive mission to promote understanding among cultures. In the early 1960s, several newly independent African countries joined UNESCO and were incorporated into the *Major Project* as part of the Eastern area. Within the musical field, initiatives needed to include African music, leading to the idea for *An Anthology of African Music*, parallel to the one dedicated to Asia.

UNESCO was not new to initiatives in the realm of recorded music. Through a collaboration with the Ethnographic Museum of Geneva, between 1951 and 1958, it promoted the important *World Collection of Recorded Folk Music* edited by Romanian ethnomusicologist Constantin Brăiloiu, which comprised forty 78 rpm records of traditional musics from the world (Bornoff 1958). The series came to an end with Brăiloiu's death, after which UNESCO decided to entrust commercial record companies to release its new record series through the IMC, its official advisory body for music policy, created by UNESCO in 1949 (Gales 2015).

The IMC cooperated with other independent non-governmental organizations in the field of music for specific projects, like the IICMSD and the International Folk Music Council (IFMC, later ICTM, now ICTMD). The co-existence of two organizations in formal relations with UNESCO in the field of what is today ethnomusicology was a reflection of the original split of the discipline into folk music studies and comparative musicology. However, the 1960s were for the discipline a dynamic decade that led to its redefinition, and these labels started to be obsolete. More than in different methodologies and approaches characterizing the old nomenclature, the difference between the IFMC and the IICMSD in the 1960s seemed to lie mainly in the musical expressions they focused on: respectively, folk music (understood as non-Western and non-classical music and dance forms) and classical or religious extra-European musics. UNESCO seemed to follow these distinct areas of competence when, in 1961, it entrusted the IICMSD with editing the mentioned *Musical Anthology of the Orient*, released by Bärenreiter-Musicaphon. The

series was generally praised for the quality of the recordings but criticized for Daniélou's commentaries on the record sleeves, in different instances considered by ethnomusicologists incomplete, incorrect, and sloppy (Picken 1962; letter by Collaer to Schaeffner, 25 Sep. 1963. AC, box 4, folder 1). The division between institutions focusing on folk or extra-European classical musics was however porous and mobile, not only as they transformed in the academia, but also in UNESCO policies, as shown by the initial entrustment of a record series on folk music to both the IFMC and the IICMSD² and the assignment to the latter of the editorship of the *Anthology of African Music*. Only in 1967, UNESCO entrusted the project of a *World Anthology of Recorded Folk Music* entirely to the IFMC (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 20 June 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). The series, finally edited by Charles Duvelle, saw just four albums, released by OCORA (Niles 2022: 425).³

Aware of the vast expertise required to direct a record series on African music but also of the critiques that ethnomusicologists addressed to the Asian anthology, Collaer posed some conditions to accept the direction of the series. He requested that his working methods be approved by the IMC and that he collaborate with Africanist specialists to guarantee the scientific value of the anthology, which he wanted to structure according to the various cultural areas of the continent (letter by Collaer to Bornoff, 25 Sep. 1963. AC, box 4, folder 1; letter by Collaer to Daniélou, n.d. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).⁴

Since the initial stages of planning the series, Collaer began networking with prominent ethnomusicologists who were experts in African music, such as Klaus Wachsmann, André Schaeffner, and Gilbert Rouget. He presented them with the series project, discussed its approach and the internal structure of the anthology based on cultural regions, requested advice and cooperation, and gathered information about existing recordings that could be suitable for the anthology. Additionally, Collaer expressed his uncertainty about the conception of this project. He wrote to Wachsmann:

For the African Sound Anthology, one thing is not clear. For me, it's necessary, for it to be a real Anthology, to make records representing the music AS IT IS, of all African cultures, whether these musics are beautiful or they are embryonic. Because there are people who are really very primitive. According to Daniélou, we can publish just things that are "beautiful" in an aesthetic way. But so, we are considering only the great art music, which is quite rare in Africa (in relation to Asia), I reckon. What do you think about this and what's your view? (Letter by Collaer to Wachsmann, n.d. [1964] AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).⁵

² The idea of a record series on folk music emerged already in 1963 ("UNESCO Anthology of African Music. Report on a meeting of experts" [draft]. AC, box 4, folder 1; Niles 2022: 425) as a collaboration between the IFMC and the IICMSD under the editorship of Peter Crossley-Holland, member of the IFCM executive Board (IICMSD Report March 1965 and IICMSD General Assembly – Director's Report, 14 July 1965. AC, box 21).

³ <https://www.ictmusic.org/publications/recordings-by-or-in-collaboration-with-ifmc-ictm#2> (last accessed on 4 September 2025).

⁴ Collaer shared with German ethnomusicologist Marius Schneider that he accepted the task of the series' direction also to guarantee the scientific value of the anthology and to attempt to unify ethnomusicologists, who at that time were divided and isolated, as he had previously done with the Colloques de Wégimont (letter by Collaer to Schneider, 8 Feb. 1964. AC, box 4, folder 1).

⁵ Capitalization in the original text in French. Translation into English by the author, as for all the following sources in French.

Although tainted by evolutionist ideas, Collaer is aware of the rarity of "classical" or "art" music conceived in a Western or Asian perspective among African traditions. This conception seemed to inspire the UNESCO anthologies, which Daniélou presented as consecrated to aesthetically "beautiful" music. Collaer considered a documentary approach, depicting the variety of African musics in their diverse forms, to be required in an anthological work. Wachsmann agreed with Collaer that «the aesthetic evaluation of recordings from Africa» was quite problematic, especially «when the aesthetic impression is to be used as the criterion for a selection of examples». Since Wachsmann considered this an issue that «touches the core of ethnomusicology», he hesitated to discuss it summarily in a letter and suggested relying on the field collector's judgment of the selection and to discuss in detail the specific recording in case of disagreement between the collector's choice and Daniélou's and Collaer's (letter by Wachsmann to Collaer, 14 Dec. 1964. AC, box 4, folder 1). Schaeffner also shared Collaer's approach, which was unbound by aesthetic principles: «to have a correct portrait of Africa, one cannot limit the series to "pure" music.» (Letter by Schaeffner to Collaer, 13 Feb. 1965. AC, box 4, folder 2).

Applying the model of the *Musical Anthology of the Orient* to the selection of African musics to appear on record seemed complex from the start. The Asian anthology was indeed conceived according to UNESCO's vision of high cultures of the world, as defined in its *Major Project*, «particularly those rooted in Asia and fashioned by an ancient, written tradition» (UNESCO 1957: 2), which could be compared and put on the same level for mutual appreciation with "Western" ones (UNESCO 1957: 5-6). UNESCO was aware that the later inclusion of African cultures on this basis was complicated: «The problem of the part to be played in the Project by non-Islamic Africa, whose cultures, in general, have no written literature or firmly established historical traditions, thus still remains to be solved» (UNESCO 1957: 2). UNESCO's approach in supporting initiatives valorizing Asian classical music was firmly shared by Daniélou. In a variety of publications, he indeed remarked on the advancement, sophistication, and long tradition of Oriental, and particular Indian music, in comparison to "Western" artistic expressions (Daniélou 1953, 1960, 1961),⁶ besides applying it to the repertoire and pieces' selection for the Asian anthology records and describing it in the sleeve notes. What seemed to lack, on both UNESCO and Daniélou's side, was a critical analysis of the application of these parameters to African musics and a flexibility in understanding their cultural value.

In a document by Daniélou introducing the two anthologies to future collaborators (fieldworkers in charge of recording, taking photographs, and writing commentaries), some principles and the vision guiding the series emerged clearly. The general introduction emphasized cultural specificity by declaring that the anthologies aimed «to present the artistic achievement of the various traditional cultures of the world in the context of their historical and cultural background» and «the technique of recording

⁶ Daniélou's positions in the promotion of world "high" cultures (and against hybridity) were in line with those of Nicholas Nabokov, by then General Secretary of the Congress for Cultural Freedom (Langenkamp 2009 and 2012).

should be faultless Hi Fi». Musical excellence, authenticity, and purity were stressed as requirements for the selected music to be featured in the anthology: «The music selected should represent the best available in a particular tradition. It should be performed by the best exponents and avoid all modern compromise [*sic!*] with external influences in matters of style, development and instruments». The historical background of the musical cultures was also considered important and collaborators were urged to «relate present day traditions to ancient culture and history (IICMSD, “Aims of the Anthologies” p. 1, n.d. [1966]. AC, box 4, folder 2).

The document included indications on the expected audience and desired reception of the series. «The records should be acceptable to the countries concerned as representing favourably their artistic music tradition». Furthermore, since the anthology was thought for the “general public”, the records should not be «merely documents on music of ethnological interest». The focus on musical artistry was one of the points on which Collaer was perplexed about an application to the African anthology. However, the document tried to overcome possible ethnomusicological skepticism by stating a position of balance between aesthetic interest and cultural documentation: «We wish to do away with the conflict between the purely ethnological document and the artistic document. Both should be equally represented. We hold that a good recording of the best music of a particular culture can also be made with all the guarantees of scientific accuracy» (IICMSD, “Aims of the Anthologies” p. 2, n.d. [1966]. AC, box 4, folder 2).

Collaer accepted the imprint of the UNESCO collection (focus on authenticity, purity, ancient traditions, high-quality recordings, artistic excellence combined with cultural interest and respect, and need for approval of the records by the countries featured), but criticized a paragraph of Daniélou’s description that assigned priority to “the higher cultures” in the records’ plan. He wrote to Jacques Cloarec, Daniélou’s assistant:

I understand the side of this paragraph concerning Asian cultures, where indeed a distinction between high cultures and more or less primitive cultures can be made. It is possible to conceive an Asian anthology where only high cultures are represented, although I would prefer to see there included people who do not have a high culture. For Africa, however, this distinction is impossible to establish. There are people more or less developed from the cultural point of view, but we have no right to neglect the most archaic countries. If we were to exclude these, it would be impossible to understand the formation and evolution of cultural states [...] I persist in following the line that I deem the best one: total representation of all cultural states. (letter by Collaer to Cloarec, 21 Jun. 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer)

Collaer’s position reflected the approach of other records dedicated to African music, for instance those in the series of the Musée de l’Homme edited by Rouget, the albums released by OCORA (Lortat-Jacob 1990) or by the International Library of African music (Tracey 1973), which presented musical expressions without grounding the selection on aesthetic principles that did not belong to the featured societies, but rather offering a survey of musical varieties. Of course, UNESCO was attentive to the reception of the records by local populations, both in terms of the impact on the preservation of musical traditions (letter by Collaer to Ames, 21 Oct. 1965. AC, box 4, folder 2) and satisfaction

with how their culture was represented (IICMSD, "Aims of the Anthologies" p. 2, n.d. [1966]. AC, box 4, folder 2). However, even if Collaer sought the collaboration of African researchers like Kwabena N'Ketia, putting the collection direction and even field documentation in the hands of Europeans could be perceived as a choice strained by coloniality, especially because the very structure of UNESCO was based on the participation and representation of all member nations, which could have been more directly involved in the preparation of the African anthology.

FIG. 1. Paul Collaer (left) and Alain Daniélou (right) with American ethnomusicologist Robert Garfias (center) at the IICMSD congress in West Berlin in 1967. Photo: Jacques Cloarec. Courtesy of the Ethnographic Museum, Berlin.

SETTING THE ANTHOLOGY PROJECT

In the plan of *An Anthology of African Music* set in 1964, Collaer, the IICMSD, and Bärenreiter had specific roles (Agreement, signed 2 Feb. 1964. AC, box 4, folder 1). Collaer, as general editor, was in charge of the records' content, which included recruiting the specialists who would provide the field recordings, photographs, and commentaries for the records, as well as supervising and revising these materials. Considering that some specialists who did the recordings were good ethnologists but not music experts, since the beginning Collaer contemplated the collaboration of external musicologists for the

preparation of the record's commentaries, or his own intervention, based on existing scientific literature (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 16 Jan. 1964. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). Collaer had to provide the record materials to the IICMSD, which, under Daniélou's supervision and through Jacques Cloarec's operative work, was responsible for the technical preparation of the record: possible editing of the recordings, preparation of the master tapes, translation of the notes that had to be in English, French, and German, and typesetting of the record sleeve (author's int. with Jacques Cloarec, 8 May 2021).⁷ Finally, the record draft was sent to Bärenreiter for producing the records and sleeves. The initial plan was to release two albums per year, with the first ones scheduled for 1964. However, due to delays in the records' preparation, the releases began in 1965. Bärenreiter, the only record company accepting the initial project of the *Musical Anthology of the Orient*, was chosen to release the African anthology because of its high standard of quality and availability. Nonetheless, since the first released albums, it appeared that its distribution system was very weak both in Europe and in the countries where the recordings were made. The distribution of the records became a recurring issue worrying the anthologies' editors and contributors and jeopardizing the very success of UNESCO's purpose of disseminating the knowledge on the musics of the world to build reciprocal understanding ("Meeting of the IICMSD Scientific Board – Session I", 15 Jul. 1965. AC, box 21).

Since the beginning of the African anthology project, Collaer engaged profusely to find recordings valuable for the anthology. He contacted various institutions that preserved recordings of African traditional music (like the Musée royal de l'Afrique centrale in Tervuren and the Musée de l'Homme in Paris), wrote to personalities he knew who had recorded in Africa, asked other ethnomusicologists (like Hugh Tracey, Klaus Wachsmann, Kwabena N'Ketia, Gilbert Rouget, and André Schaeffner) about their recordings and for suggestions on current research in the field. In this correspondence, Collaer delineated the desired characteristics of the recordings and the record structure.⁸ First, the recordings had to be of high technical quality. This involved the use of advanced equipment (ideally Nagra recorder and Neumann microphones, as those the IICMSD employed) and implied the skill of the collector to obtain recordings as clean as possible from disturbing ambient noises and without distortions (letter by Collaer to Arom, 10 Dec. 1964. AC, box 4, folder 1). The recordings had to have «a musical interest and not only a purely documentary one» (letter by Collaer to Zemp, 5 Mar. 1964. AC, box 4, folder 1). They should not be too short: the desired length was at least three minutes, to allow the listener to get familiar with the music and appreciate it (letter by Collaer to Hiernaux, 27 Oct. 1964. AC, box 4, folder 1). Finally, deciding the order of the tracks in the record, the fieldworker had to consider «an alternance producing diversity» (letter by Collaer to Zemp, 5 Mar. 1964. AC, box 4, folder 1). Collaer also advised the fieldworkers on the length of the pieces in relation to formal development and repetitions: «long pieces are desirable if their form is developed enough. For short forms, even if based on the repetition of

⁷ Available at <https://recherche.smb.museum/detail/2931379/interview-jacques-cloarec> (last accessed: 25 October 2025).

⁸ Since the beginning of 1965, a "Note" containing this information was circulated among fieldworkers.

variants, the piece should not in principle be below three minutes» (letter by Collaer to Tracey, n.d. [Jan. 1965]. AC, box 4, folder 2). Also, «in the case of short pieces, it is necessary, despite the repetition without variants, to give an example long enough for the listener to understand the style and the absence of variants» (letter by Collaer to Arom, n.d. [Jan. 1965]. AC, box 4, folder 2).⁹

These parameters were simple to follow for recordings made during ongoing fieldwork, such as in the case of Hugo Zemp and Simha Arom, who could adhere to these guidelines while choosing the music to record, controlling the standard of recording, selecting the tracks, and setting up the sequence for the record. However, these conditions were harder to meet in the instance of existing recordings, like those by Denyse Hiernaux-L'Hoëst and Monique Brandily, preserved at the Musée royal de l'Afrique centrale, or those by David K. Rycroft. These recordings originated for other purposes than the release on a record, mostly for research documentation, and the collectors were sometimes ethnologists, like Hiernaux-L'Hoëst, not well-versed in recording techniques and technology, which at times was not up to the state of the art. Similar problems concerned the material accompanying the recordings: photographs and commentary notes. In the case of current research, the fieldworker was easily able to document photographically the performers and instruments featured in the audio, and s/he was usually a trained ethnomusicologist, able to prepare notes about the musical traditions and the individual pieces featured in the album. On the other hand, in the case of older recordings, sometimes photographs documenting the chosen pieces were missing and the collector was not competent to write the musicological description of the tracks. While the selection of the pieces was negotiable by Collaer and the IICMSD with the collector and it was possible to obtain commentaries from experts and visual documentation from other alternative sources (although not portraying the featured performers), the quality of recordings was an essential issue. The technologies available in the studio of the IICMSD allowed for limited operations of noise reduction and distortion regulation, so fieldwork recordings had to be of high audio quality from the start (author's int. with Cloarec, 8 May 2021).

The recordings' technical quality emerged as central since the first record projects of the anthology. For Daniélou, normally reporting UNESCO's perspective, technical quality was an essential criterion determining the selection of the recordings for the records (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 6 May 1966 and 31 May 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer), while Collaer considered it important but not more than the cultural value of the music.

⁹ Finally, other indications, later elaborated by the IICMSD, regarded the editing procedures of the recordings: it was recommended that the pieces be complete performances and not cut; if this was required for a piece too long, a «moderate use of fading is desirable». Additionally, «when making cuts, it is preferable to cut in the middle of a piece rather than to shorten it at the beginning or the end» (IICMSD, "Notes for the guidance of authors", n.d. [1966]. AC, box 4, folder 2).

FIG. 2-3. Covers of the first two albums of the *Anthology of African Music: Music of the Dan* and *Music from Rwanda*.

The First Two Records: Audio Quality and Cultural Value of Recordings

While Collaer was in complete charge of the editorship of the African anthology, his contacts with the IICMSD were not limited to the final delivery of the audio, visual, and textual materials for each record. Indeed, he was regularly in touch with the West Berlin Institute about the selected recordings, images, and commentaries (AC, box 4). This was partly due to the advice that Daniélou could offer thanks to his experience as the editor of the Asian anthology and his direct link with UNESCO, but also based on the technical expertise in Berlin, where the editing of the tapes and the preparation of the master tapes, as well as the setting of the images, was carried out by Jacques Cloarec (author's int. with Cloarec, 8 May 2021; "Work on records" [IICMSD internal document], n.d. [1964/65]. AC, box 5, folder 5).

The Music of the Dan, the first record of the Anthology, was dedicated to the music of the Dan people from the Ivory Coast recorded by Hugo Zemp, and was a smooth collaboration between the recordings' collector, the series' general editor, and the IICMSD. Collaer got in touch with Zemp, by then a young doctoral student in Ethnomusicology in Paris, thanks to André Schaeffner and Gilbert Rouget. Zemp was conducting his fieldwork in the Ivory Coast and agreed to make recordings and photographs for a record, of which he also authored the commentaries. Collaer was very satisfied with the Swiss ethnomusicologist's recordings and selection and supported him also beyond this record project. Daniélou evaluated the recordings as «excellent. The beginning and ends are very skillfully done, the sonic level and the quality perfect. The selection also seems [...] very good from the point of view of the listener» (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 30 Nov. 1964. AC, box 4, folder 1). Zemp's record was later also acclaimed by the critic. In 1966, it won the Grand Prix International du disque of the Académie Charles Cros and a mention, together with the series' second record, in the golden medal given to the African anthology by the Deutsche Schallplattenkritik (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 4 Oct. 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

The second record project of the African anthology, *Music of Rwanda*, based on the recordings of Denyse Hiernaux-L'Hoëst, required more time and effort to be completed. Besides the collector's scarce time to focus on the project, during the preparation of this disc, there were disagreements between Collaer and Daniélou on the pieces selected for the record, because of the recordings' technical quality. Hiernaux-L'Hoëst had made recordings in the field during a mission in 1954-55 with Belgian anthropologist Jacques Maquet, who also took pictures, on the account of the Institut pour la Recherche Scientifique en Afrique Centrale (IRSAC), where they both worked. In 1964, Collaer made a first choice of the recordings, based on their technical quality, and then Hiernaux-L'Hoëst finalized the selection (letter by Collaer to Hiernaux, 4 Mar. 1964 and 27 Oct. 1964. AC, box 4, folder 1).

For Daniélou, the technical quality of the selected recordings was not very good, although the tracks were interesting. He ascribed the poor audio level to the "disastrous" quality of the recording device and microphones (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 11 Mar. 1965. AC, box 4, folder 2). In 1955, ten years before the record project, the IRSAC did not own advanced recording devices nor technicians to set up the available ones (letter by Hiernaux to Daniélou, 28 Jul. 1965. AC, box 4, folder 2). In most recordings, there was a

buzz, probably due to the electricity engine, and other noises such as scratching or a saturated microphone. Daniélou suggested to Collaer removing the noises when possible and discarding the remaining pieces (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 11 Mar. 1965. AC, box 4, folder 2). Collaer stressed that the recordings were precious testimonies of Tutsi music, whose performers had disappeared or gone into exile because of Hutu violence in the period 1959-62 (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 17 Mar. 1965. AC, box 4, folder 2). Finally, Collaer decided to discard exclusively four recordings whose quality was disturbing the listening and to improve the sound quality «in the cases where it was possible and necessary» by removing some noise or cutting the track at the beginning or end. In contrast to Daniélou's comments, he considered that in some recordings where a hissing (*souffle*) could be heard, it was due to the recording environment and not disturbing the listening but part of the performance space. Additionally, he held that the murmured singing connoting one of the tracks was a characteristic of the song itself, meant for the performer and not for others to listen (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 4 Apr. 1965. AC, box 4, folder 2). Daniélou accepted the selection and the editing asked by Collaer and eventually evaluated the complex as «musically excellent»; he only suggested changes to the sequence of the pieces so that each section of the record would start with the technically best recordings (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 9 Apr. 1965. AC, box 4, folder 2).

Some negotiations also took place regarding the sleeve notes of the record, particularly about involving Maquet for the ethnological commentary – since he had published important works on Rwandan society based on documentation collected during that mission – and German ethnomusicologist Robert Günther for the musicological notes, as he had just published an analysis of Hiernaux-L'Hoëst's recordings. However, Hiernaux-L'Hoëst proposed writing all the commentaries and using Maquet's pictures featuring the recordings' performers; Collaer integrated the musicological analysis of the recordings, in particular the tonal diagrams of some pieces, with information from Günther's book (correspondence Collaer-Hiernaux-Daniélou-Günther, 1965. AC, box 4, folder 2).

Despite the mentioned golden medal awarded to the African anthology for the Rwanda and Dan albums by the Deutsche Schallplattenkritik in 1966 and some positive reviews,¹⁰ this record's reception was not fully positive. It caused a quite negative review by Merriam (1967), who critiqued the choice of the music as not the best selection of Rwandan music variety, the poor audio quality, and flaws in the notes, especially in comparison to the first record of this series. According to Merriam, despite the value of the album's original field recordings documenting disappearing or disappeared musical practices, a more interesting music selection was possible, also based on available commercial recordings. Furthermore, he criticized the recording quality, especially in some pieces, as too low for a UNESCO record series. Finally, Merriam complained about the laconic commentary notes, which contained inaccuracies and did not identify the ethnicity of the performers. What he appreciated the most was Maquet's photographs.

¹⁰ For instance, those by David Rycroft (1967) and Marcel Doisy (1967) – the latter praising the album but connecting it with personal information on Hiernaux-L'Hoëst that appears uncalled for and taints her fieldwork with colonialist nostalgia.

Surely, the quality of Hiernaux-L'Hoëst's recordings was below the level achievable in the mid-1960s with a Nagra recorder and Neumann microphones and, despite the selection of the best pieces and some editing operations, some tracks on the record, in particular n. 4, 11, 16, and 17, contain disturbing noises or are poorly recorded. Collaer was well aware that the technical quality was not at the level required by the UNESCO series. Nonetheless, he considered the recordings' documentary and cultural value – presenting to big audiences the musical traditions that the violent revolution marking Rwanda's transition to Independence had almost annihilated – to go beyond technical considerations. As Merriam remarked, the notes were shorter and less detailed than Zemp's record. This was probably for the best, given the approach and tone of Hiernaux-L'Hoëst's commentaries, still based on a racist conception of Rwandan society – akin to the one that led to the very violence of 1959-1962 and, later, the 1994 genocide. Although she did not explicitly mention races, Hiernaux-L'Hoëst remarked on the stereotyped different physical appearance and culture: «There is nothing to surprise us in the fact that the three social groups of Rwanda, so contrasting in their genetics and their culture, should differ in their forms of musical expression» (Hiernaux-L'Hoëst n.d.). While this is obviously unacceptable today, it was still rooted in the academic community of the 1960s and indeed not criticized by Merriam, who would have liked to read in the notes the ethnic identification of each performer, despite the record's structure in three sections (Tutsi, Hutu, and Twa), and hierarchical organization with Tutsi first on top (8 tracks), Hutu second position (5 tracks), and finally the Twa (3 tracks).

DEVELOPING THE AFRICAN ANTHOLOGY, THE IICMSD STRUCTURE, AND ETHNOMUSICOLOGY

The first years of the African anthology project corresponded to some institutional readjustments of the IICMSD, whose collaboration with Collaer became tighter. Already in 1964, one year after the foundation of the Institute, preoccupations emerged on the possible cessation of financial support from the Ford Foundation after the initial three years of funding. The discussions of the IICMSD with West German foundations and Berlin authorities to obtain alternative funds showed that these institutions required the Institute to be confined within national frames of activity and budget in order to fund it. This condition betrayed the IICMSD's purposes of international cooperation and intellectual independence, as defined also by its partnership with UNESCO. To show the IICMSD's commitment to internationality and justify its special status to both the Ford Foundation and German authorities, the idea of creating international branches of the IICMSD in other countries emerged. One of these was the Belgian one, established in 1965 by Collaer at the Musée royal de l'Afrique centrale in Tervuren ("Convention entre le Musée royal de l'Afrique centrale à Tervuren et l'Institut d'Etudes comparatives de la musique", 23 Oct. 1965. AC, box 5, folder 5). The Belgian branch was dedicated to African music and, besides editing the UNESCO Anthology, it systematically cataloged the recordings of the Tervuren Museum and supervised research projects on African

musics.¹¹ In the same year, Collaer was also elected as chairman of the IICMSD Scientific Board (IICMSD official document, March 1965, p. 25. AC, box 21).

The main activity of the IICMSD Belgian branch was the editorship of the African anthology, which continued to pose challenges to Collaer. The records' preparation was usually slow and difficult because of the numerous parties involved (collector/author of notes and photographs; general editor, IICMSD, Bärenreiter) and the presence of the tapes, images, and texts partly in Brussels, where Collaer lived, and in Berlin, at the IICMSD, according to the progress of each project. Collaer tried to smooth out this complicated organization by assuming all responsibility for the preparation of definitive audio, visual, and textual material before sending it to Berlin (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 8 Mar. 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). However, sometimes problems emerged with corrections on the commentaries, which, because of the tight schedule and delays, could not pass the approval of the author, as it happened in the case of the album on Chadian music by Brandily (letter by Brandily to zur Lippe [IICMSD], 18 Jan 1968. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). Finally, Bärenreiter was at times slowing down the preparation of the records once it received the master tapes. However, despite all these difficulties, the series continued rolling.

The collaboration with ethnomusicologists conducting their fieldwork in those years was mostly successful. In addition to Zemp, who also prepared a second record for the series,¹² Israeli-French ethnomusicologist Simha Arom contributed two discs to the anthology. Not only was Collaer enthusiastic about Arom's recordings, but Daniélou was also «thrilled by the technical and artistic quality of his work» when he received the first tapes with a selection of recordings (letter by Daniélou to Arom, 26 Jul. 1965. AC, box 21). Also the collaboration with American ethnomusicologist David W. Ames seemed promising since the beginning and two records on Nigerian Hausa music were planned, since both Collaer and Daniélou agreed on the musical interest and technical quality of his recordings (letter by Collaer to Ames, 9 Jun. 1966. AC, box 24). With other ethnomusicologists, the collaboration was less smooth. Brandily's recordings were criticized by Cloarec and Daniélou as having a hiss (*souffle*), but Collaer clarified that it depended on the regulation of the pre-amplifier (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 6 Jul. 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer), so the record preparation proceeded.

The collaboration of the IICMSD with Zemp and Arom continued in the following years, beyond the projects for the African anthology, with the two ethnomusicologists contributing several albums to the other UNESCO series, *Musical Sources* and *Musical Atlas*, both directed by Daniélou. As mentioned, the 1960s were a central decade for the (re-)definition and establishment of ethnomusicology in academia. This included the definition of the specific professionalism of the ethnomusicologist, combining fieldwork methods with musical analysis and theoretical writing, differently from previous researchers on traditional music who analyzed recordings made by someone else in the

¹¹ Another branch was the Italian one in Venice, which in 1968 became the Istituto Internazionale di Studi Musicali Comparati (IISMC) hosted by the Giorgio Cini Foundation. In the IICMSD internal papers, also a Japanese and a French branch are mentioned, the latter based at the Musée Guimet and dedicated to the teaching of Asian music. These planned branches were never developed.

¹² For an account of Zemp's decade-long experience with recording and releasing albums, see Zemp 1996.

field, as the so-called armchair ethnomusicology. The professionalism and expertise of the new generation of ethnomusicologists – such as Zemp and Arom, who were in their thirties during the 1960s – made them ideal collaborators for the series because they could provide recordings of musical interest, high audio quality, along with significant photographs from the field, and scientific commentary on the music featured.

Nonetheless, these collaborations could be surprising, considering the fracture between ethnomusicology in academia and the more practical work on traditional musics (concerts and tours, besides records and publications) carried out by the IICMSD on the imprint of Daniélou's positions. Daniélou's work was held in low esteem by some ethnomusicologists, especially from France and Germany (letter by Schaeffner to Collaer, 28 Feb. 1964. AC, box 4, folder 1; letter by Schneider to Collaer, 5 Feb. 1964. AC, box 4, folder 1).¹³ On the other hand, although Daniélou sought the support of German comparative musicologists to establish the Belin Institute in the early 1960s (letter by Daniélou to Donald J. Grout, 8 Aug. 1965. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer), he later expressed very boldly his criticism of ethnomusicology (Daniélou 1971). Daniélou's collaboration with young ethnomusicologists like Zemp and Arom can be understood within the framework of the specific record projects marked by a commonality of interest (dissemination of traditional music), vision (presentation of African cultures displaying their musical variety), and standards (technically best recordings possible), along with their outstanding outcomes. Record projects did not necessarily involve the discussion on broader issues, as for instance musical refinement and purity from external influences, which were very dear to Daniélou and essential parameters in the music selection for the records, but started to be deconstructed by ethnomusicology in those years. And when these issues appeared in the preparation of a record, a compromise could be found (author's int. with Simha Arom, Venice, 31 May 2019; author's int. with Claorec, 8 May 2021).

The discussion of such issues, however, emerged on the higher level of editorship of the series and indeed was faced by Collaer in planning the African anthology following UNESCO's and Daniélou's requirements. For the French orientalist, who always grounded his point of view in UNESCO's positions, the music selection of the anthologies had to be based on aesthetic relevance and refinement. This perspective followed a Western or Asian conception of music as divided into "high" or "classical" and "folk", while it also reflected the diverging focus of his IICMSD and the IFMC in those years. As mentioned, since the start Collaer considered this vision rarely applicable to the traditional repertoires of Sub-Saharan Africa, where very few traditions that could be labeled as "classical" existed. His approach was rather guided by a documentary principle, aiming to feature the various expressive forms of the African continent. In search of a solution allowing the release of African repertoires not fitting with the Anthology's criteria, Collaer discussed with Daniélou the idea of having a record series dedicated to scientific audio documents, where recordings like those by Hiernaux-L'Hoëst could appear. He also

¹³ Criticism of Daniélou's positions was, however, not limited to France. Among the contestations of his positions, it is worth mentioning the negative remarks of Italian ethnomusicologist Roberto Leydi (1991: 309).

suggested to Luiz Heitor Corrêa de Azavedo, Brazilian musicologist working at the UNESCO Department of Cultural Affairs, to create a record series of “documents”, along with the “artistic” one (the African anthology). The documentary series «should include non-artistic musics in the sense traced by High Cultures, but which are not so important if one wants to give a true overview of African music. [...] We should not be reproached for giving a truncated or distorted representation of African musical culture» (Letter by Collaer to Corrêa de Azavedo, 20 Mar. 1965. AC, box 4, folder 2). Exploring new possible collaborations for another record series dedicated to African traditional music was also based on the widespread dissatisfaction (among collectors, Collaer, IICMSD, IMC, and UNESCO) of Bärenreiter’s distribution of the Anthologies’ records not only in Asia and Africa, but also in Europe (“Meeting of the IICMSD Scientific Board – Session I”, 15 Jul. 1965. AC, box 21). These projects would never materialize, but a new series, proposed by Daniélou to UNESCO, would instead start some years later, the mentioned *Musical Sources*.

THE IMPASSE ON THE ZULU AND SWAZI RECORDINGS

The friction between Collaer and Daniélou’s positions concerning the technical quality of the recordings and their artistic refinement reached its peak during the preparation of two records on South African music based on Rycroft’s recordings among the Zulu and Swazi, which also marked the final stages of the series’s records released in the 1960s.

The collaboration between Collaer and Rycroft started in 1965. Rycroft proposed recordings for four records including not only traditional music but also urban neo-traditional music, whose study Rycroft was a pioneer (Rycroft 1956 and 1958). To this proposal, Collaer specified that not everything seemed usable in the Anthology because the UNESCO collection dealt only with «old traditional art and... avoid[ed] examples of modern acculturation» (letter by Collaer to Rycroft, 14 Dec. 1965. AC, box 4, folder 2). Rycroft made a new proposal of two records: the first one included Zulu singing accompanied by different types of musical bows; the second Swazi, Zulu, and Xhosa vocal (solo and choral) music. Collaer found the music very interesting, but he feared that both records could be too monotonous in style for an audience not used to those music styles (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 20 Jan 1966. AC, box 4 folder 2). So he thought of different options and modified the sequence of the pieces of the Zulu album to provide some variety (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 9 Feb. 1966. AC, box 5 folder 5). Also, he was concerned about the shortness of some Swazi pieces, but he thought they were essential to document Swazi culture, although relying on a racist perspective:

Since the imagination of certain African people of really primitive culture is not very developed, sometimes their music consists of one or two phrases indefinitely repeated without variation. Hence, it is important to report this cultural status by supplying a certain number of examples of this type of music. (Letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 22 Mar. 1966. AC, box 4 folder 2).

In principle, Daniélou was not opposed to introducing some shorter pieces, partly because brief fragments could sometimes be more engaging than longer, repetitive ones. However,

he cautioned Collaer that for UNESCO, it was crucial to choose pieces where «the musical element... prevails over the documentary one» because, in UNESCO's view, the records needed to attract a broad audience to African music, not just specialists (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 24 Mar. 1966. AC, box 4, folder 2). At a deeper listening of Rycroft's recordings, Daniélou specified that the problem was not the type of music, but rather the recordings' technical quality: they were not done with a Nagra, but the real issue was «the total lack of the art of recording [...] It's there, I think, the real problem – the artistic sense that allows one to do justice to what one wants to present, even as a document.» (Letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 20 Jun. 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). While Daniélou's critiques emphasized the technical aspect, the aesthetic one also emerged as he underlined that «here we have a series of very short recordings, sequences of pieces that are almost similar, interesting especially as documents...» (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 31 May 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). Similar to the case of the Rwanda record, Collaer understood that Daniélou's criticism was not only based on the technical aspect of the recordings, so he underlined that the Zulu and Swazi people do not have a variety of music styles comparable to those in Central Africa. Furthermore, he pointed out that their traditional music remained unknown to the wider public since only their music influenced by European military and Protestant music was promoted, exactly because Swazi and Zulu music was indeed «very rudimentary, without development». For Collaer, «if we are doing an anthology of African music, we do not have the right to eliminate very important documents like these, which are for everyone a revelation». Finally, he asked Daniélou to request flexibility from UNESCO to include these "scientific documents" in the series whose general editorship was under his name; if this principle was not accepted, he thought they could receive criticism from musicologists (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 7 Jun. 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

Because of these opposing stands, the preparation of the record(s) of South African music remained blocked. Collaer was convinced of the value of the South African recordings and explored other solutions. He sent Rycroft's recordings to the RAI studios in Turin to improve their technical quality through professional editing (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 9 Sep. 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). With Rycroft's edited recordings, the project of an album was reconsidered, featuring one side with Swazi music and the other with Zulu. However, Cloarec thought that it was still lacking good and complete pieces and suggested asking Rycroft whether he had better recordings of Zulu music to include (letter by Cloarec to Collaer, 24 Nov. 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). Rycroft agreed to suggest some alternatives, but thought that some Zulu recordings had to be absolutely included (letter by Collaer to Cloarec, 18 Dec. 1967, AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

Finally, Rycroft's recordings never appeared in the African anthology, and the series was discontinued by UNESCO. Nonetheless, Collaer was able to publish the two records in 1968 and 1969 as part of the new scientific record series of the Ethnomusicology section freshly established at the Tervuren Museum and independent from the IICMSD.¹⁴

¹⁴ Because of the lack of UNESCO support to the Belgian branch and the threat of completely closing it, in 1968 Collaer negotiated the establishment of the Ethnomusicology section at the Tervuren Museum. Based

An Anthology of African Music – first part (1965-1969)		
Album	Collector	Bärenreiter-Musicaphon Catalogue Number
<i>The Music of the Dan</i>	Hugo Zemp	BM 30 L 2301 [1965]
<i>Music from Rwanda</i>	Denyse Hiernaux-L'Hoëst	BM 30 L 2302
<i>The Music of the Ba-Benzélé Pygmies</i>	Simha Arom	BM 30 L 2303
<i>The Music of Ethiopia I – Music of the Ethiopian Coptic Church</i>	Jean Jenkins	BM 30 L 2304
<i>The Music of Ethiopia II – Music of the Cushitic Peoples of South-West Ethiopia</i>	Jean Jenkins	BM 30 L 2305
<i>The Music of Nigeria – Hausa Music I</i>	David W. Ames	BM 30 L 2306
<i>The Music of Nigeria – Hausa Music II</i>	David W. Ames	BM 30 L 2307
<i>The Music of the Senufo</i>	Hugo Zemp	BM 30 L 2308
<i>The Music of Kanem</i>	Monique Brandily	BM 30 L 2309
<i>Musics of the Central African Republic</i>	Simha Arom	BM 30 L 2310 [1969]

TABLE 1. List of the albums released in the series *An Anthology of African Music* in the 1960s.¹⁵

TECHNICAL QUALITY, ARTISTIC REFINEMENT, AND THE VALUE OF TRADITIONAL MUSICS: THE DISCONTINUATION OF THE AFRICAN ANTHOLOGY

Daniélou articulated his criticism of the Rwanda and South African records and later UNESCO's feedback on the African anthology by grounding them in the principles guiding the anthologies according to the Organization's aims. His position was delicate as the IICMSD was the bridge between UNESCO and Collaer: he tried to balance his negotiations with them, explaining Collaer's reasons to UNESCO and proposing to him alternatives for releasing the records, as well as exploring ways for a better reception of the series in African countries. Talking for UNESCO also gave Daniélou leverage to influence Collaer's choices without explicitly undermining his position as the general editor of the African anthology. The intense correspondence between Collaer and Daniélou, especially between 1967 and 1968, exposed their positions further and ultimately led to the

on the experience, approach, and network developed as an IICMSD branch, the section was financially supported by the Belgian government and directed by Jos Gansemans (letter by Collaer to Burnier, 6 Sep. 1968. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

¹⁵ The records are listed following their progressive catalog number. The albums' year of release is not indicated on the records nor in the Bärenreiter-Musicaphon catalog. As per the contract, two records were released annually between 1965 and 1969, but this pace was not always respected. These albums are available on YouTube (last accessed 24 October 2025), except for the first two (the third one, *The Music of the Ba-Benzélé Pygmies*, can be found as the 1998 CD re-issue of the original record).

conclusion of their collaboration, parallel to the discontinuation of the African anthology by UNESCO.

Already in 1966, Daniélou reported to Collaer UNESCO's dissatisfaction with the African anthology and the possibility of its discontinuation. Negative comments regarded the audio quality of the African series compared to the Asian one, most probably based on the Rwanda record, despite the disclaimer on that album explaining the music selection as dictated by the uniqueness of the recordings (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 6 May 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). The following year, «both anthologies were actively listened to at the UNESCO General Direction and the African anthology was criticized for being too ethnographic and of insufficient technical quality and of not being conform to the aims pursued by UNESCO, which are not to collect documents having a scientific value, but to create an interest on the whole of the audience for the culture of different countries» (Letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 12 Sep. 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). Collaer was annoyed by this criticism, which he deemed unfounded: the recordings «were not chosen for their scientific value but because they were what those people produced of most beautiful» and, except for a pair of pieces with some technical defaults in the Rwanda record, the other released albums were of high technical quality (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 16 Sep. 1966. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

To address the possibility of African governments' dissatisfaction with the records, Daniélou and Collaer agreed to seek their involvement, to stimulate «an African sentiment that it is their collection and not a foreign study on their traditions and customs» (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 14 Jan. 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). Collaer asked for the collaboration of experts of the Tervuren Museum to critically read the commentaries of the last discs, highlight sensitive or offensive content, and correct them (letter by Collaer to Cloarec, 6 Jun. 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). However, the hoped-for collaboration with African governments never materialized. On the contrary, criticism from within UNESCO also manifested about the music selection and the commentaries of the two records of Ethiopian music by British ethnomusicologist Jean Jenkins, which aroused the disappointment of an Ethiopian delegate (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 23 Oct. 1967. AC, box 4, folder 1). Collaer refused UNESCO African delegates' critiques, arguing that they were not music experts; also, he received Merriam's negative review of the Rwanda record with contempt, stating that it was the best-seller of the series. He understood UNESCO's irritation about unflattering commentaries, but he deemed their employees not knowledgeable in music matters and their remarks not deserving to be taken seriously (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 9 Nov. 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

Once again, Daniélou balanced his delicate position, restating the artistic purpose of the anthologies. He understood Collaer's vision in contrast with UNESCO, but thought that if it was really irreconcilable, it had to be declared openly since the series was under UNESCO's aegis. Appealing to their long friendship, he wished further collaboration (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 13 Nov. 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). Collaer insisted that UNESCO had to accept African musics as they were, or else terminate the African anthology project or appoint a new general editor, because in Sub-Saharan Africa,

there was no art music like in Europe or Asia (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 14 Nov. 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

In November 1967, Daniélou was informed that UNESCO had decided to discontinue the Anthologies. The criticism of the African records by African delegations at UNESCO harmed the Organization's consideration of the series (IICMSD, "Report of the Director and General Secretary, 1967". AC, box 4, folder 1). Furthermore, the *Major Project* had ended the year before and a new orientation spread through the UNESCO. According to Daniélou, there was no more interest in projects based on the ideas of continents and nations, as the Asian and African anthologies, which were thus discontinued. On the other hand, his project for a new series, *Musical Sources*, centered on world "big cultural currents" was supported by UNESCO, but a closer collaboration with the Organization was also required; African records, in particular, had to be submitted to a committee (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 28 Nov. 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). Collaer criticized UNESCO's lack of stability in its cultural policies caused by the plurality of positions of its members. He also considered the IMC ineffective and resigned from it. Finally, he deemed unacceptable that the records had to be reviewed by a committee, whose efficacy he doubted (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 7 Dec. 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). Furthermore, Collaer considered false the idea, at the base of UNESCO dissemination projects, that European, Asian, and African music had to be considered equal. In his view, world traditional music represented the European musical past, from which European music had developed further. Although UNESCO's "quite utopian" vision was worth interest and he accepted the IICMSD's dissemination role, he did not understand Daniélou's refusal to include ethnomusicological works in the Institute and wondered whether his connection with UNESCO was so strong that he was subjected to its imperatives. He considered that a stalemate about the scientific or non-scientific position to adopt (letter by Collaer to Daniélou, 18 Dec. 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

The tension between Daniélou's and Collaer's finally burst about the approach to the study of traditional musics of the world, clashing on its subject (traditional musics broadly understood, including folk ones, or exclusively art musics) and scientific method (the ethnomusicological one or a comparison based on "impartiality"). The IICMSD report for the year 1967 stated: «We have been able to create for ourselves a place which stands clearly apart from the field of ethnomusicology and is also quite distinct from that of folk music studies» (IICMSD, "Report of the Director and General Secretary, 1967". AC, box 4, folder 1). Collaer understood the IICMSD position away from ethnomusicology and folk music studies as an exclusive focus on «non-European art musics and in a way functional to their diffusion outside Asia». The IICMSD's field of interest, hence, did not actually include African musics because there was «no African art music», and its approach did not correspond to that of the Belgian branch, which worked according to scientific ethnomusicological methods and concerns. Considering this, Collaer offered a last mediating option by assigning an ethnomusicological role to the Belgian branch whilst the Italian one dealt with non-European music dissemination; alternatively, he suggested closing the branch in Tervuren (letter by Collaer to Daniélou and Burnier, 22 Dec. 1967. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

Daniélou answered him that the terms "musical ethnology" and "folklore" were applied in too wide a sense to non-European musics and they could appear tendentious. Ethnology did not deal, in principle, with aesthetic values that concern music and he did not find it logical that Western musical art was evaluated following aesthetic criteria and music of other civilizations according to ethnological ones. Daniélou saw his position as based on the reevaluation of musical languages based on impartiality, which he deemed as «the only attitude that can be called scientific». On this stand, he had founded the IICMSD, which was devoted to some of the work not done by universities and museums (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 1 Jan. 1968. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

Collaer tried to highlight the difference between "music ethnology" and "ethnomusicology", but Daniélou replied that that difference was appreciated only in some milieux while in others they were considered equivalent and that "ethnomusicology" covered a variety of topics which could be better subdivided and named (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 15 Jan. 1968. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer). Finally, Collaer certified his complete incompatibility of vision and approach with UNESCO, whose directives the IICMSD followed strictly. He did not approve of the division between art and folk music, which was obsolete, and stated that «traditional musics are also artistic». He wondered why UNESCO and the IMC did not specify any guidelines, clarifying their position, when they offered him the direction of the African anthology. Also, he considered the IICMSD's work to promote Asian artists in Europe as valuable, but as «an impresario's work, not of a man of science or a musician». In the end, he resigned as President of the IICMSD Scientific Council (letter by Collaer to Daniélou and Burnier, 22 Jan. 1968. AC, box Correspondance Paul Collaer).

CONCLUSIONS

The end of the project of the *Anthology of African Music* corresponded to the clash of visions and approaches between Collaer and Daniélou/UNESCO, and to the end of the Belgian branch, from which the Ethnomusicology Section of the Musée royal d'Afrique centrale of Tervuren emerged. The collaboration between Collaer and the Berlin Institute formally terminated when his position as Director of the Scientific Committee came to a natural end in 1969, although he had wanted to resign already the year before, at the peak of the contrast with Daniélou. Despite the interruption of this collaboration and the deep scientific disagreements, Collaer remained a friend of Daniélou and supported him when Raymond Burnier, Daniélou's lifelong partner and Secretary General of the IICMSD, suddenly died in 1969.

The personal friendship between Collaer and Daniélou was surely an important factor in gluing together a collaboration doomed to fail from the beginning. Despite Collaer's initial caution, demand for acceptance of his methods, and doubts on UNESCO's and Daniélou's conception of the traditional music to be featured in the African anthology, he accepted the general editorship of the series. He considered the project of the African anthology important and appealing, even if he did not evaluate UNESCO's work very positively; Daniélou's trust in the project convinced him. On the other hand, Daniélou relied on Collaer's reputation for establishing the respectability of the Berlin Institute,

whose Scientific Council the Belgian musicologist chaired, and considered his networks precious for tracing fieldworkers and recordings for the African series. Since the beginning, UNESCO's scope in the anthologies project was clear to Daniélou, who had direct contact with the Organization and aligned with its aims in the field of traditional music, while Collaer received information through Daniélou's mediation and understood UNESCO's vision and inflexibility only during the preparation of the series.

Reciprocal esteem and personal friendship between Collaer and Daniélou delayed the emergence of profound disagreements about the study of traditional musics. Since the start of their collaboration, Collaer's position appeared in line with ethnomusicology, as it was establishing in the 1960s: the documentation of musical traditions including their various repertoires, flanked by musical analysis and ethnographic data, as well as the revocation of the distinction between high and folk musics with a predilection for "authentic" expressions. More outdated for that time, and at times also tainted by remarks that today sound racist, was Collaer's evolutionary understanding of the music of the world, based on the conception of "primitive" musics being a sort of testimony of older historical stages of development of more "advanced" musics, like Western classical music. Daniélou was external to academic ethnomusicology: his study of Indian classical music and immersion in Indian culture molded his approach and vision to traditional musics more broadly. This determined his focus on "art" or "classical" musical repertoires and aesthetic aspects but also the firm belief in the equality of musical traditions that displayed artistic finesse, opposing the Eurocentric belief in the backwardness of "Other" musics. Furthermore, Daniélou's position in relation to the academic research on traditional music (as music ethnology, folk music studies, or ethnomusicology) developed during the 1960s, also through his direct contact in Europe with scholars in these fields. He related to German comparative musicology because he wanted to show the equal value of classical Asian music, and indeed the adjective "comparative" appears in the name of the Berlin institute. However, he did not share the prevailing emphasis in the ethnomusicological literature of the time on ethnological elements or the use of Western transcription systems, which he viewed respectively as distractions from aesthetic appreciation and as misrepresentations of non-Western musical systems. Furthermore, he adopted a more interventionist approach to musical traditions, which included the promotion and dissemination of live performances – activities that were not considered part of ethnomusicology at the time. His stand on these matters clarified during the late 1960s and emerged clearly in his book *The Situation of Music and Musicians in Countries of the Orient* (Daniélou 1971).

UNESCO's position – on the African anthology as it emerges from the analyzed correspondence, and more broadly on its *Major Project* – was also conditioned by its focus in the late 1950s on Asian cultures and interpellations, whose characteristics and requests forged both the *Major Project* and the Asian anthology. There was a lack of knowledge of the African context and cultures, as well as superficiality in enlarging the *Major Project* to Africa on those premises. Finally, the terrible distribution and promotion of the two anthologies outside Europe did not help in fostering mutual appreciation of «cultural and artistic values of universal interest» (letter by Daniélou to Collaer, 13 Nov. 1967. AC, box

Correspondance Paul Collaer), especially in the African continent, where the records rarely reached local cultural institutions.

Ten years after this disruption, UNESCO decided on the continuation of the African anthology on the condition that the commentaries be reviewed by the Organization and that the consent of the concerned countries was obtained. The fact that Collaer's work was not considered bad or, at least, was reevaluated, is shown by the fact that he was asked to continue the editorship of the series (letter by Cloarec to Collaer, 24 Jan. 1979. IISMC, box 26). Rather, a deeper involvement of African countries and their representatives at UNESCO was needed. The restart of the series was very slow (the record Nigeria III, based on Ames' recordings already submitted in the late 1960s, was not released until 1986) and was not free from some of the tensions that marked the first part of the series.

The contrasts that emerged in the 1960s over the editorship of the African Anthology provide insight into broader and more complex debates concerning UNESCO's cultural policies, prevailing conceptions of traditional music and its promotion, and the shaping of ethnomusicology as a distinct academic discipline. This article also aims to contribute to the development of a new line of inquiry into the history of ethnomusicology. In particular, the many large-scale discographic projects focused on traditional world musics during that period – including the African Anthology – warrant further investigation in relation to ethnomusicologists' efforts to disseminate the results of the extensive recording campaigns, which characterized the phase of "urgent ethnomusicology", and to secure greater visibility and recognition for the discipline itself.

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